

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Rendon Davila**FIRST NAME:** Gabriela C.**PROGRAM CODE:** DSDD**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** Period 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

ESSENTIAL CONCEPTS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Cleenewerck and Gulma's *ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (2019) described the basics of academic writing and explained the importance for students to plan, organize, how to avoid plagiarism and formatting the work. The text is a remarkable compilation of guidelines, reference lists, examples and a Chicago style crib sheet, a valuable resource for any student. The authors explained that any good essay starts with a question, the evidence supporting the argument, and reminded us that "essay writing is not a linear process" (EUCLID 2019, 1) but a wash and rinse until we discover the proper way to answer the question.

The first chapter provides a roadmap to organize and plan the essay, with clear instructions on how to expand each of the topics, what to focus on and how critical thinking helps students to connect the evidence to the argument while balancing "opposing views" (EUCLID 2019, 1–4). Chapter two tackles the problem of plagiarism, what it is, emphasizing that the only way to avoid it is to cite the work we use. This chapter provided examples on how to cite, what kind to use, tips for citations and most importantly, how to paraphrase correctly (EUCLID 2019, 5–13).

Chapters five through seven clarified grammatical structures and proper writing styles, and the differences in the use of the English language depending on the country of origin (EUCLID 2019, 14–36). On this topic, they warned about different English versions used throughout the document, which is a reflection of the academic source and not a grammatical mistake, except for those in the sample paper, which were left intentionally for the students to identify and learn from the feedback provided in parenthesis. Lastly,

chapter eight and nine include the Chicago Manual Style Crib Sheet and a list of Latin Abbreviations commonly used, respectively (EUCLID 2019, 44–61).

Additionally, the course included a video facilitated by Pr. Cleenewerck showing how to use the Microsoft Word for formatting according to EUCLID requirements.

2) ACADEMIC WRITING

a) Planning the Essay

Cleenewerck and Gulma describe the basic elements of essay writing emphasizing the importance of preparing the material and note-taking techniques to avoid future mistakes on citations and references. Furthermore, they advise starting early, focusing on gathering relevant material and actively reading, that is, asking questions regarding the author's tone or historical setting, and on the relevance of the material toward the topic (EUCLID 2019).

The way they describe how to construct a plan and how to start writing reminded me of hurdles and snags, challenging. Gathering material, skimming through books, highlighting phrases and starting a collection of index cards is the unattractive side of research. However, having good index cards is not enough to write a good essay. What we do with the information and how we process it is what matters.

It surprised me how clear are the guidelines in the document; they are a clear roadmap for us to follow with instructions included, contrary to other courses that I took in previous universities. Cleenewerck and Gulma offered a three-block structure focusing on what is important to address on each rather than the length or format of the paragraphs. The introduction block presents the question at hand with a summary of what lies ahead, enticing the audience. The core block showcases supporting evidence and develops the argument. Lastly, the closing block wraps up key points and re-states the answer. This structure allows me to include as much evidence or arguments to answer the main question.

After reading the first section, I discovered two personal flaws when writing an essay. First, I do not use mind mapping, and second, I have not yet learned how to “evaluate differing arguments” (EUCLID 2019, 2) nor correctly explain how opposing views relate to my conclusion. Still, I do play devil's advocate when writing my notes and take into account other researcher's angle, so I do not overlook counterarguments. I am pleased that I still have room for growth.

b) Plagiarism

The course pack provides clear examples of when to use citations and how to cite properly. At the beginning of my experience as a graduate student, I used in-text citations instead of paraphrasing for two main reasons. First, I was an international student with a vocabulary that was not extensive, and it was difficult for me to find the right words to

express the central argument in a way that any reader could understand. Second, I am dyslexic; hence, putting into my own words a text that takes me three times to understand is hard. After reading the tips about quotations, sure enough, my essays were boring and dull at the beginning of my graduate studies. Still, I believe I made the right decision to sacrifice originality than paraphrasing something wrong, resulting in accidental plagiarism.

Despite my learning challenges, I developed a personal method for paraphrasing. I start annotating while reading and note-taking, on a separate card I write down direct quotes with proper references and put it away. Days later, I analyze the quote, summarize it on a different card and include keywords that help me sort the material. The next day, I read the summary and write down what I understood, avoiding using words from the previous card as much as possible. This lengthy process helps me to chunk the information so I can understand it and be able to express it in my own words.

A topic that caught my attention in this chapter is the use of signal phrases regarding plagiarism and paraphrasing. I was not aware that using “pointing out,” “stressing,” or any related verb plus the name of the author was a signal to paraphrasing. While the coursework includes an example with quotation marks, it does not provide an example involving paraphrasing, which would be of great benefit.

c) Proper Style

Cleenewerck and Gulma alert us of wordiness and remind us to center our attention on addressing the question at hand with clear sentences and avoiding boring paragraphs or random quotes.

There were three points on this section that caught my attention. First, focusing on presenting a clear and concise argument, contrary to previous courses where instructors demanded elaborated structures and intricated words to reflect graduate-level writing. Indeed, addressing the research question should be our priority as doctoral students in the social sciences. Second, to stay away from using the passive voice as much as possible. However, I find the use of passive voice useful when I try avoiding being accusatory or over political. Lastly, avoiding the use of direct quotes to introduce an essay because it gives the impression that the student is “looking for a way to fill some space” (EUCLID 2019, 14). I believe the abuse of direct quotes on essays has to do with strict outlines and weak thesis. The majority of schools in the United States teach students to stick to the script and word quota to have a passing grade. So, instead of spending time researching for key topics, central arguments and findings to have a strong thesis, students browse for quotes to embellish the essay.

The rest of the section is a good reminder of common rules while writing an essay. The use a period, quotation marks, the difference between “its” and “it’s” or “your” and “you’re,” the use of a comma, written numerals, and the use of “I” versus “me.”

d) Formatting

Every industry demands a quality standard for products and services; academia is no different. Publishing houses and international organizations request specific formats to show consistency throughout their journals and divisions, respectively. Formatting styles provide uniformity in this global world, helping authors to submit original work to more publishing houses. The use of consistent styles helps the audience to navigate documents, locate findings or references easily. Furthermore, it provides homogeneity for the corporate world, retail and lately to digital marketing where contributors follow guidelines setting aside their personal style and showcasing the company style instead.

Although formatting brings more positive attributes to academic writing, one of the main critiques I have is the word count as a standard of quality. Kafka's *Metamorphosis* has about 25,000 words, Machiavelli's *The Prince* approximately 47,000 and Umberto Eco's *The Name of the Rose* over 180,000 and all of them are of brilliant content. Hence my question: Is it necessary to have lengthy essays to be seen as scholarly worthy? I believe that it is possible to answer a research question without filler paragraphs or to abuse in-text quotes without being forced to cap word quotas.

What I found more helpful from this section was the CMS Crib Sheet. I was impressed by how Dr Scribe managed to summarize the entire manual in only eleven pages. I took especial interest in compound words, especially regarding hyphenated words and prefixes as well as the use of italics. On the later, I noticed that foreign languages that are of common use in English are no longer in italics, like *laissez-faire*. However, it doesn't mention anything regarding Latin like *ad-hoc* or *a priori*, terms that I have seen in both formats. Furthermore, I paid particular attention to the use of abbreviations, whether they go inside the parenthesis or not, and the recommendation to use the least amount of them to avoid confusing the reader.

3) CONCLUSION

Truth to be said, when I learned that I had to write an essay about academic writing I cried. Memories from past ghosts knocked on my door torturing me with esoteric words, grammatical rules and literary terms. I assumed English courses were a thing of the past, and that the path toward a doctoral degree would only focus on political science, development and global issues. I misinterpreted the information regarding the course. Nonetheless, I started reading the document with the idea that academic writing relates more to research than to creative writing, where the main goal is to convince the audience of our argument, much like an attorney aims to persuade a juror and ultimately win the case. Such an approach allowed me to set my frustration aside and bypass cognitive bias.

Overall, *ACA-401D The Coursepack: Period 1* surprised me because of the clarity of the concepts, the tips and the variety of examples. However, I noticed that throughout the reading formatting is of great importance but the document itself does not reflect a homogeneous style, perhaps it was implicit when the authors warned us about the different

English versions used throughout the document. Moreover, I was surprised not reading about self-plagiarism, which unfortunately, is a common practice among students. While some students call it economy of scale or being smart, using a fragment of prior essays on recent works without proper citation, or submitting the same essay in different courses without permission from professors is plagiarism. I believe addressing this topic in the future would benefit students at all levels because whether accidental or not, plagiarism brings to light student limitations, displays the unethical character of a person, and it is just plain wrong.

I am glad that my fear was unfounded. This reading demystified what they taught me on previous courses and opened windows of opportunity to grow as a student. As a result, I discovered new tools to tackle personal challenges in learning, like mind maps to explore different arguments. I learned the importance of balancing opposing views, and that academic writing is more than matching evidence with arguments or filling pages with examples and quotes to impose a view.

Academic writing is the structured presentation of ideas supported with strong evidence taking into account opposing views.

REFERENCES

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